

Additional files in support of the “[Best of Both Worlds](#)”

In 2024, the ICSP ratified the 'Best of Both Worlds' (BoBW) proposal for the formal regulation of *Candidatus* names within the [ICNP](#). The outcome of the vote on this proposal, as well as the preceding online discussion, has been documented in the [IJSEM](#). In response to the debate, however, the authors of the BoBW proposal prepared additional files, which are publicly available in a single PDF document here.

1. Online petition „Support the Best of Both Worlds“

See <https://www.ipetitions.com/petition/support-the-best-of-both-worlds>. Note that the number of signatories in favour of BoBW (and against the acceptance of the SeqCode by the [ICSP](#)) is more than one order of magnitude higher than the number of signatories in support of the paper by Whitman and Venter (2024).

2. Letter of Support for BoBW from the [World Federation of Culture Collections](#)

See below.

3. Letter of Support for BoBW from the [U.S. Culture Collections Network](#)

See below.

4. Detailed rebuttal of the arguments against BoBW by [Whitman and Venter \(2024\)](#)

See below. Note that Figure 1 in the Whitman and Venter (2024) paper is of particularly low intellectual quality, raising questions about why it passed the journal's peer review process and why it was supported by renowned scientists.

WORLD FEDERATION FOR CULTURE COLLECTION

To the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

Reference: “Best of Both Worlds” changes to the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes

28 May 2024

Dear Sir/Madam,

The WFCC Executive Board wishes to express our stance regarding the proposed amendments to the *International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes* (ICNP), titled “Best of Both Worlds”.

In February 2020, the WFCC Executive Board addressed the *International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes* (ICSP) concerning proposed alterations to the ICNP. Enclosed below is the complete text of the letter sent at that time.

The adjustments deliberated by the ICSP in 2020 aimed to allow a genome sequence (and potentially even a single-gene sequence) to serve as the nomenclatural type for a species or subspecies with a validly published name. Formerly, under the ICNP, valid publication of a species or subspecies name necessitated the deposition of a strain, known as the type-strain, in two separate culture collections located in different countries. The proposed transition from physical entities – living organisms – to experimental outcomes – genome sequences – as nomenclatural types would have brought about fundamental changes to prokaryotic nomenclature. In our letter from 2020, we outlined several arguments opposing this modification. Similarly, other organizations such as ECCO articulated similar points or presented additional arguments against the proposal.

Consequently, the WFCC Executive Board objected to the 2020 proposal to amend the ICNP. In accordance with our recommendations and those of numerous others, the ICSP rejected the proposal by a decisive majority vote (17:6).

Unfortunately, the decision made by the ICSP resulted in the publication of the “Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes Described from DNA Sequence Data,” commonly known as “SeqCode,” in 2022. This code not only contradicts the ICNP but also shares essentially the same shortcomings as the proposal rejected by the ICSP in 2020. Most of the arguments outlined in our 2020 letter, which are attached below, are equally applicable to SeqCode.

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The WFCC Executive Board harbours significant concerns, not only regarding the existence of two competing prokaryotic nomenclature codes but also about the adverse effects of SeqCode on the motivation to culture and deposit biological material. This, in turn, negatively impacts the reproducibility of experimental outcomes, such as genome sequences.

The regulations pertaining to access to biological material remain a central concern for the WFCC. Concerning nomenclature, we wish to underscore that “validly publishing” a name under SeqCode due to the inability to deposit the type - strain under Rule 30 of the ICNP, owing to legal constraints in the country of origin, does not resolve the underlying issue. Other researchers would still be unable to replicate the study of the strain because it remains inaccessible. The proper solution to this problem lies in the adoption of legislation that is more conducive to scientific endeavours in these countries.

In 2020 we emphasized that “WFCC values molecular investigations related to unculturable diversity including detection of new phylum/class/family/genera/species through such information. Since in these instances live material generation is not possible, molecular information can be utilized and the ‘candidatus’ status can be created for these species until they can be isolated from environmental sources.”

Lowering the standard for validly publishing names of species or subspecies by allowing genome sequences, rather than accessible living cultures (from which high-quality genome sequences can be obtained at any time), as nomenclatural types, is unnecessary for naming, let alone describing uncultivated prokaryotes. This was evident in 2020 and remains evident in 2024. Although the regulation of *Candidatus* names by the ICNP may be insufficient, any practical issues associated with applying the *Candidatus* concept may or may not stem from inadequate regulations. Some *Candidatus* names may be incorrectly formed by their authors, and certain instances of purported instability may arise from alterations in taxonomic viewpoints, over which a code of nomenclature holds no jurisdiction.

In 2024, Arahal et al. introduced a concept known as the “Best of Both Worlds” approach. If endorsed by the ICSP, this approach would maintain the existing criteria for valid publication while establishing regulations for *Candidatus* names in a manner analogous with validly published names.

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Specifically, implementation of the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal by Arahal et al. (2024) would expand the regulations within the ICNP to ensure that:

- clear regulations determine which *Candidatus* name applies in cases of synonyms.
- homonyms between centrally registered *Candidatus* names and validly published names are prevented.
- *Candidatus* names are reused when a name for the same taxon is proposed for valid publication.
- authors of a *Candidatus* name remain acknowledged even after a name for the same taxon is successfully proposed for valid publication.

Thus, the “Best of Both Worlds” approach illustrates that to effectively regulate the nomenclature of prokaryotes lacking cultures or where satisfactory deposition is unattainable, there is no necessity to lower the standards for valid publication. The WFCC Executive Board strongly commends this approach. Specifically, the Board acknowledges that the “Best of Both Worlds” approach acknowledges the efforts of those who formally propose *Candidatus* names based on metagenomic or similar studies, as well as those who subsequently culture and deposit the same taxa. This approach appears to be the most equitable, catering to the needs of all parties, recognising everyone's contributions, and duly acknowledging the superiority of living cultures over sequences – including genome sequences – as nomenclatural types. Under the “Best of Both Worlds” framework, there remains ample incentive for cultivation and deposition, crucial for ensuring scientific reproducibility and the availability of cultures for future research endeavours.

The “Best of Both Worlds” represents a crucial compromise that holds promise in reinstating a unified code of nomenclature for prokaryotes. In any scenario, such a compromise stands preferable to the SeqCode, which, as comprehensively outlined by Arahal et al., shares many of the same drawbacks as the proposal dismissed by the ICSP in 2020, and moreover, conflicts with the ICNP.

Therefore, the WFCC Executive Board emphatically urges the ICSP to embrace the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal.

On behalf of the WFCC Executive Board,

Ipek Kurtböke

WFCC President

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Appendix: Original 2020 letter by WFCC

On behalf of the WFCC's Executive Board, I would like to forward our views on the proposed changes in the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes.

WFCC is not a decision-making authority in prokaryotic, eukaryotic and viral taxonomy; however, as an end user it is impacted by the decisions made by relevant international committees. In this instance replacing type strain deposition by only nucleotide sequence data, we believe can weaken the robustness of bacterial taxonomy for the following reasons:

1] Reliable identification of the type strains for a given genus and species deposited after that for the genus in question:

It should employ polyphasic methods including genome sequences. Accordingly, only physically available reference material can ensure error free identification via reanalysis of the material. Moreover, due to the current availability of powerful identification methods replacing the previously popular ones, the older data can be reassessed at any time. The use of such powerful techniques to re-sequence a species is not possible without the preserved biological material.

2] Compliance with international rules and regulations:

Collections must follow national and international laws such as biosafety, biosecurity (including dual-use organisms), and quarantine regulations as well as complying with the import and export restrictions. All these regulations contain appendices with lists of names of organisms. Any access, utilization and sending of an organism requires a risk assessment with the confirmed identity of the organism. Restricting deposition and identification to whole-genome sequences alone would limit vital information on the growth characteristics, physiology, morphology and many more features of the organism. Technology-based approach can also discriminate collections and institutions from developing countries who may not have access to this technology.

3] Deposition of the genome and other molecular data:

Genome information has weighty importance however, quality control has to be ensured via high standards for whole-genome sequences at the global level. Culture collections so far have made significant progress in developing standards for authentication, preservation and tracking of the origins of the deposited material. They regularly exchange information and share knowledge and experience with collections through international, regional

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meetings and networks. WFCC thus would welcome open discussions on commonly used standards for genome data, its acquisition, analysis, storage and access to ensure reliability.

We also would like to draw attention to the currently encountered difficulties in gaining access to the sequence data (Digital Sequencing Information or DSI). While access to the (reference) material is regulated by national and international agreements and laws, present views on the access to DSI vary substantially. Restricted access to the DSI thus can be in conflict with the principle of “unrestricted access” of the ICNP. As a result, if deposited biological material is available, the DSI can be recreated in another location for the same species.

4] WFCC values molecular investigations related to unculturable diversity including detection of new phylum/class/family/genera/species through such information. Since in these instances live material generation is not possible molecular information can be utilized and the “candidatus” status can be created for these species until they can be isolated from environmental sources.

In conclusion, the WFCC’s Executive Board members recognize the importance of molecular data and DSI, however, the integrity of such information can only be ensured, and validity can be confirmed with the presence of deposited biological material.

Kindest regards

Dr Ipek Kurtboke
WFCC President

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7 August 2024

To: International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

From: U.S. Culture Collections Network

Subject: “Best of Both Worlds” proposal to the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes

On behalf of the U.S. Culture Collection Network (USCCN), I would like to convey our support for the 2024 Arahall et al. “Best of Both Worlds” approach for the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP). USCCN is a NSF-funded Research Coordination Network that brings together scientists working with laboratory based collections of living microbes.

The adoption of this “Best of Both Worlds” proposal would expand the ICNP to ensure that:

- Formal regulation with the *Candidatus* name applies in instances of synonyms
- Prevention of homonyms between (centrally registered) *Candidatus* names and validly published names
- *Candidatus* names would be reutilised promptly upon the proposal of a name for the same taxon for valid publication
- Authors of a *Candidatus* name would retain recognition even after a name for the same taxon is proposed for valid publication.

In this way, the “Best of Both Worlds” approach demonstrates that to comprehensively regulate the nomenclature of prokaryotes for which cultures are not yet available – or cannot be satisfactorily deposited – it is not necessary to lower the requirements for valid publication. The USCCN greatly appreciates this approach. In particular, the USCCN notes that this proposed approach recognises the work of those who formally proposed *Candidatus* names because of metagenomic or other studies, as well as the work of those who later culture and deposit the same taxa. This seems to be the fairest approach, meeting everyone's needs, recognising everyone's contribution, and considering the superiority of living cultures over sequences – even genome sequences – as nomenclatural types. Furthermore, there would still be sufficient incentive to cultivate and deposit microbial cultures to ensure scientific reproducibility and the availability of cultures for future generations.

The USCCN continues to have significant concerns about the presence of two competing prokaryotic nomenclature codes. The USCCN recognises the importance of establishing a stable nomenclature for uncultivated prokaryotic diversity. However, the ICNP has long incorporated the *Candidatus* concept for such scenarios. Instead of implementing drastic changes to the notion of valid publication, which could result in a division within prokaryotic nomenclature, addressing gaps in the *Candidatus* concept seems to be a more suitable approach for tackling the challenges associated with naming yet uncultivated prokaryotes.

Thank you for the opportunity to provide comments on this proposal on behalf of the living microbial community.

Respectfully submitted,

Dusti Gallagher
USCCN Project Manager

On behalf of the USCCN Steering Committee members:

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Kyria Boundy-Mills, Phaff Yeast Collection, University of California-Davis

Kellye Eversole, International Alliance for Phytobiomes Research

Neha Potnis, Auburn University

Matthew Ryan, Genetic Resource Collection, CABI

Response to the “Commentary on the proposed Section 10 amendments to the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes regarding *Candidatus* names” by W.B. Whitman and S.N. Venter

Short Summary. – A 2024 article by Whitman & Venter presents a criticism of the “Best of Both Worlds: a proposal for further integration of *Candidatus* names into the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes” study and the proposals by Arahall et al. (2024) for emending the ICNP. The paper by Whitman & Venter is biased; Whitman & Venter have not addressed any of the criticisms raised against the proposed SeqCode, which is not recognized by the ICSP but nevertheless forms one basis of the argumentation of Whitman & Venter. Our rebuttal here shows that the criticisms of the “Best of Both Worlds” by Whitman & Venter lack substance, partially because the proposals of Arahall et al. have been misrepresented. Few people have contributed to or endorsed the article by Whitman & Venter; they may wish to re-consider, as their potential good intentions will be served much more sustainably by the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal. “Best of Both Worlds” is fully compatible with and respectful to previous ICSP decisions; the proposed SeqCode is not. “Best of Both Worlds” appropriately cares about the quality of nomenclatural types; the proposed SeqCode does not. “Best of Both Worlds” results in an informative and fair code; the proposed SeqCode does not.

Below, we will address the comments raised by Whitman & Venter (2024). The original text of their article to which we specifically refer is given each time in italics and after a “W&V” prefix.

W&V: Abstract – *Amendments were proposed to the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP) in January [Arahall et al. (2024) Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol. 74: 006188] that would cause major changes in the treatment of Candidatus names. The amendments introduce Section 10 to name taxa whose names cannot be validly published under the ICNP because of the absence of type strains. This section creates a parallel ‘pro-nomenclature’ and formalizes alternative material which could serve as nomenclatural types. When conspecific isolates of taxa with Candidatus names are deposited in culture collections as type strains, the names can be validly published, and it is required that the same Candidatus name be used. While the amendments are promoted to provide stable names and rules of nomenclature for uncultivated genera and species, the system is deeply flawed. It removes the permanent association between names and types, which will make the meaning of names imprecise and ambiguous. It creates ‘pro-nomenclature’, which is confusing and unnecessary. Since many taxa which cannot be validly named under the ICNP can already be named under the SeqCode, it duplicates and creates overlap with an established nomenclatural system without providing tangible benefits. As the SeqCode recognizes names formed under the ICNP, the ICNP should recognize names formed under the SeqCode as they have done for the Cyanobacteria named under the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants (ICN). For these reasons, we urge the members of the International Committee of Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP) to reject these amendments.*

Summary of our response:

- The proposed SeqCode significantly reduces the motivation to cultivate and also deposit the designated type strains of newly proposed species or subspecies, which constitute the reference standards for prokaryotes, thereby endangering the replicability of scientific outcomes, the possibility of using cultures to test cellular, as well as nucleic acid sequence-derived hypotheses, and the availability of cultures to future generations. It devalues the efforts of those who do the often difficult and innovative work of cultivating and depositing microorganisms. The acceptance of the proposed SeqCode by the ICSP is therefore not an option; it would also make the work of the IJSEM meaningless. Whitman & Venter (2024) fail to address any of those issues.
- The recognition of cyanobacterial names validly published under the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants (ICNafp) by the ICNP cannot serve as a precedent to recognize the proposed SeqCode, as argued by Whitman & Venter, since the ICNafp also demands physical material (preserved specimens) as nomenclatural types for validly published names and has repeatedly rejected proposals to consider DNA sequences as nomenclatural types.
- The proposed SeqCode by construction contravenes the ICNP and therefore has created an “overlap with an established nomenclatural system”, namely the ICNP, itself. The proposed “Best of Both Worlds” emendation of the ICNP does not contradict any previous ICSP ruling and would result in a code that retains the motivation to cultivate and deposit and remains more informative than the SeqCode because the “pro-nomenclature” status clearly distinguishes between names based on available biological type material and names based only on experimental outcomes (i.e., DNA sequences).
- Under the ICNP, there is no absolutely “permanent association between names and types”, and the ICNP already envisages the replacement of nomenclatural types when *Candidatus* names are replaced by validly published names. The replacement of types under “Best of Both Worlds” has a clearly defined purpose and can occur only under clearly defined conditions. Therefore, it does not make “the meaning of names imprecise and ambiguous”. The graphical approach used by Whitman & Venter (2024) to demonstrate this alleged problem is misleading. They also incorrectly presuppose that a code of nomenclature regulates the circumscription of a taxon. Even Whitman’s (2016) original proposal envisaged the exchange of a sequence by a culture as nomenclatural type whenever possible.
- In fact, Whitman & Venter (2024) even admit that our proposal “addresses a major concern in prokaryotic biology by providing a system of stable naming for taxa that cannot be deposited in culture collections.” Furthermore, Whitman & Venter (2024) fail to conclusively demonstrate any disadvantage of “Best of Both Worlds”.

W&V: Main text. – *In 2020, a proposal to amend the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP) to allow DNA sequences to serve as nomenclatural types was rejected by the International Committee on the Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP) (Sutcliffe et al., 2020, Whitman, 2016). This proposal would have enabled creation of stable names for taxa for which type strains cannot be deposited in two international culture collections, a requirement of the current ICNP.*

Major kinds of taxa that would have been affected included the uncultivated known from metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) and single-amplified genomes (SAGs); fastidious prokaryotes that cannot be deposited because the collections lack the expertise, resources, or desire to accession them; and cultures isolated from countries with legal barriers for their distribution. Many of these taxa had Candidatus names, which are provisional names outside the legislative portion of the ICNP that lack standing in nomenclature. Therefore, in response to the need for stable naming of taxa that currently cannot be formally named under the ICNP, a committee under the auspices of the International Society for Microbial Ecology developed the SeqCode, an alternative code of nomenclature in which DNA sequences serve as types (Murray et al., 2020, Hedlund et al., 2022, Whitman et al., 2022). The SeqCode was designed to complement the ICNP so that it would be possible to create unified taxonomies of uncultivated and cultivated prokaryotes with a shared nomenclature.

Not an argument. – The proposed SeqCode (Hedlund et al. 2022) has a variety of significant disadvantages, which have been compiled and described in detail by Arahal et al. (2024). Whitman & Venter did not attempt to address any of these criticisms. These criticisms remain valid.

For instance, the SeqCode claims to address three different situations: (a) uncultivated organisms; (b) cultivated organisms which culture collections have refused to hold; (c) organisms whose type strain for legal reasons cannot be deposited in an accessible way. Papers in favour of the SeqCode highlight that it targets uncultivated prokaryotes and also countries that prohibit depositing type strains (if they were isolated in that country), in adherence to Rule 30 of the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023). However, what finally matters are the regulations embedded in the SeqCode itself.

It is important to understand that the proposed SeqCode does not restrict its application to uncultivated prokaryotes or strains that cannot be deposited and made accessible. The SeqCode defines itself as a code that uses genome sequences as nomenclatural types (Hedlund et al. 2022).

As the ECCO board (Sutcliffe et al. 2020) wrote in 2020 about the earlier proposal (Whitman 2016) to accept genome sequences (and potentially other DNA sequences) as nomenclatural types of species or subspecies in the ICNP:

‘If the proposal is accepted, it will no longer be strictly necessary to deposit any material in public collections, be it type-strains, DNA-extracts or environmental samples. This of course does not mean that we think that efforts to isolate and study new species in culture would be completely discarded nor that all scientists who have regularly been depositing strains will suddenly stop to do so, but overall the motivation to do all that is needed for depositing type-strains in a public collection will decrease. The proposal allows for later replacement of a type sequence by a type strain when the latter becomes available, but in our experience, we believe that in practice this will be forgotten or, worse, simply ignored. This should be a major concern to all stakeholders, especially in the light of climate change and the accelerated loss of biodiversity.’

Compared to the earlier proposal (Whitman 2016), the proposed SeqCode does not even allow “for later replacement of a type sequence by a type strain”. The only possible taxonomic incentive to later cultivate and deposit the same organism would be to propose an emendation of the taxon description. However, this is unrealistic because:

- a) emendations are optional and descriptions of most taxa never get emended;
- b) when conducting an emendation, it would be optional to base it on a culture;
- c) when basing an emendation on a culture, it would be optional to deposit that culture.

For these reasons, the possibility of emendations does not solve the problem highlighted by the ECCO board and others (Sutcliffe et al. 2020) at all.

In fact, the proposed SeqCode does not only remove the incentive to cultivate and deposit an organism that has received a “validly published” name under the SeqCode when it was still uncultivated. The SeqCode is already being used as the basis for “validly publishing” the names of organisms that have been cultivated but not deposited in international culture collections for access by the scientific community.

In a 2023 article (Viver et al. 2023) we find the statement:

‘For the second cultivated, but yet unsuccessful deposit in a second culture collection we propose *Salinibacter pepae* sp. nov. ... We expect that in the course of the months after this contribution has been published, the deposit of the strain ESAV49^{Ts} is finally successful. After the second deposit we will append a corrigendum to this manuscript to definitively validly publish the name also under the ICNP.’

This name has been “validly published” under the proposed SeqCode. We do not yet know if the authors will try to validly publish the name under the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023), as well. This is a good reminder that the SeqCode is not a code solely for the uncultivated. We see it being used to try to get around a situation wherein a deposit is not available, or not yet available. The example also demonstrates an inconsistency: the name is claimed to be “validly published” and yet the attempt to validly publish the name is also announced. This is the direct consequence of contradictory codes. Most importantly, the example already demonstrates the importance of the ICNP in not recognizing the proposed SeqCode so as to maintain the incentive to deposit already established cultures.

Likewise, the SeqCode *devalues* the work of those who cultivate and deposit, particularly difficult-to-cultivate prokaryotes. Because of the SeqCode, researchers who cultivate and deposit now come into competition with others who can “validly publish” names based on a MAG alone. Those who do the hard work therefore agree that the ICSP should not accept names “validly published” under the SeqCode; see, e.g., *Promethearchaeum* (<https://microbiologysociety.org/blog/appreciation-towards-culture-collections.html>). There are people who do cultivate and deposit the first representative of, e.g., a phylum, and their interest may well be that the phylum is then named after their genus and not named after a just a MAG.

“Best of Both Worlds” creates an incentive to suggest names for uncultivated prokaryotes and also maintains an incentive to cultivate, deposit and name those cultivated prokaryotes. For this reason, “Best of Both Worlds” is the fair and informative solution. Giving equal status to names based only on a MAG or other determined digital sequence information (DSI) and names based on a deposited culture is neither fair nor effective. Fairness does not simply mean treating everyone equally. It means treating everyone in the same situation equally. If you give one product to one customer for \$20 and 5 minutes later the same product to another customer for \$10, you have treated the two customers equally (you gave them the same thing). But you have not treated them fairly. The first of

the two customers may indeed get very upset about this.

W&V: *The proposal of Arahal et al. (Arahal et al., 2024) is an alternative to the SeqCode and is currently open for discussion on the ICSP Slack channel. After July 4 2024, it will be voted on by the ICSP. For the reasons discussed below, we believe that this proposal will greatly damage progress in prokaryotic systematics, and we urge the ICSP to vote against it. This opinion is endorsed by the signatories listed below.*

See below. – We will respond to the content of these criticisms below.

The number of people who have endorsed the article by Whitman & Venter (2024) is quite small. We urge all supporters of the proposed SeqCode to review their standpoint in view of our arguments. Our online petition “Support the Best of Both Worlds” has attracted much more support (<https://www.ipetitions.com/petition/support-the-best-of-both-worlds>). Eminent scientists share our views, including microbiologists from Brazil, India and South Africa, who are affected by national regulations that make it difficult for them to validly published names under the ICNP.

W&V: *The amendments in the newly proposed Section 10 introduce Candidatus names into the code to name taxa whose names cannot be validly published under the ICNP because of the absence of type strains deposited in two or more international culture collections (Arahal et al., 2024). In contrast to the previous informal nomenclature for Candidatus names, Section 10 creates a parallel ‘pro-nomenclature’ which regulates the priority amongst taxa with Candidatus names. However, the pro-validated names will not compete for priority with validly published names. It also requires publication of Candidatus names in the IJSEM and designation of types, which were not previously required. However, when isolates of taxa with Candidatus names are deposited in culture collections to serve as type strains, the names can be validly published. The Candidatus designation must be dropped and the species name used as the validly published name for the conspecific isolate. In this way, the system provides stable names and rules of nomenclature for uncultured genera and species. Thus, it addresses a major concern in prokaryotic biology by providing a system of stable naming for taxa that cannot be deposited in culture collections.*

Supports our proposal. – We are grateful for this positive assessment. To us, this indicates that once the criticisms of our proposal have been refuted or addressed, it should be endorsed, given its merits, even by the supporters of the Whitman & Venter (2024) article.

We particularly note that Whitman & Venter did not attempt to address any of the criticisms of the SeqCode listed by Arahal et al. (2024). Since these criticisms of the SeqCode apparently remain valid, our proposal is the better option, given that the criticisms of our proposal can be refuted or addressed. While the SeqCode contravenes the ICNP (Göker et al. 2022), the “Best of Both Worlds” proposals are fully compatible with previous ICSP decisions (Sutcliffe et al. 2020).

W&V: *There are very serious criticisms of the proposed Section 10. It accomplishes its goals by introducing a number of novel devices into the ICNP, each of which are problematic as described below. 1) It creates ‘pro-‘nomenclature. 2) It requires changes in types for Candidatus names if they become validly published, and it allows changes in the category of types for Candidatus names. 3) It introduces requirements to ‘reuse’ names. Each of these are problematic, will be difficult to apply, and cause confusion. They also fail to solve any important practical problems.*

See below. – As reiterated below, each of the measures envisaged by the proposed Section 10 has a precise meaning and are beneficial to prokaryotic nomenclature.

W&V: *The purpose of nomenclature is to create names that will be used in scientific literature. While Candidatus names have become widely used in the last twenty years, Section 10 changes the meaning of the term, a distinction that may not be appreciated outside of the systematics community.*

Not correct. – Whitman & Venter (2024) do not provide evidence for the claim that Section 10 changes the meaning of the term “*Candidatus*”. In fact, Section 10 does nothing of the sort (Table 1).

In contrast, Section 10 differentiates between pro-validly published *Candidatus* names and other *Candidatus* names. All previously known *Candidatus* names would remain *Candidatus* names. They would be used as before.

Table 1. Comparison of definitions of the term “*Candidatus* name” between the 2022 revision of the ICNP and the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal. There is no actual difference in the concepts, the proposed Section 10 is just more precise.

Appendix 11, ICNP

The provisional status *Candidatus* ... should be used for describing prokaryotic taxa for which more than a nucleic acid sequence is available but for which the requirements for valid publication of a name according to the Code are not met.

Proposed Section 10, Rule 66

The *Candidatus* status should be used to propose names of prokaryotic taxa for which some information is available (Rules 67–68), but for which the requirements for valid publication of a name under Rule 27(3) are not met.

W&V: *It also introduces a complicated ‘pro-nomenclature’ where Candidatus names can be ‘pro-legitimate’, ‘pro-correct’, and ‘pro- validly published’. As a consequence, for the foreseeable future there will exist Candidatus names that are ‘pro-illegitimate’ and Candidatus names that are ‘pro- validly published’ without ready means to distinguish them. Given the complexity, many scientists will ignore these distinctions.*

Not an argument. – This cannot seriously be used as an argument against the “Best of Both Worlds” because it applies equally to the vast majority of prokaryotic names that are already in use.

There is already no “ready means” to distinguish a legitimate name from an illegitimate name other than looking it up in the IJSEM or in an associated database like LPSN (Meier-Kolthoff et al. 2022). There is no “ready means” to distinguish a validly published name from a not validly published name either because many authors may not use quotation marks to indicate not validly published names and since the status of the name may change by validation. Accordingly, one would also look up the name in the IJSEM or in an associated database like LPSN, hence the importance of a unified code and database, which would be jeopardized with parallel systems.

Exactly the same situation would be introduced regarding the distinction between pro-validly published and not pro-validly published *Candidatus* names and regarding the distinction between pro-illegitimate and pro-legitimate *Candidatus* names. One would also look up the name in the IJSEM or in an associated database like LPSN.

The complexity is, therefore, not significantly increased. In fact, the parallels between the terms pro-validly published, pro-legitimate and pro-correct on the one hand and validly published, legitimate and correct on the other hand should be obvious.

A more general problem with this whole argument about increased complexity is that it overestimates the value of simplicity. Just one example: The ancient Greeks distinguished four elements: air, earth, fire and water. Now we distinguish between over 100 chemical elements. That is, of course, far more complex than the four elements. And yet we choose the modern periodic table. Why is that? Because it is more informative. Similarly, the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal results in a more informative (and fairer) code than any attempt to give names based on MAGs and names based on an isolated and deposited strain the same status in nomenclature.

W&V: *While codes of nomenclature often allow multiple kinds of types, most do not permit changing the types of names because it makes the names ambiguous and leads to confusion. For instance, Article 7.2 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants (ICN) states: “A nomenclatural type (typus) is that element to which the name of a taxon is permanently attached, whether as the correct name or as a synonym” (Turland et al., 2018).*

Not an argument. – As obvious from its context, this sentence refers to names *validly published* under the ICNafp (Turland et al. 2018). Validly published names under the ICNP are not affected by the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal.

When considering other codes, it is important not to compare apples and oranges. How well the ICNP is aligned with the ICZN (Ride et al. 2000) and the ICNafp (Turland et al. 2018) in terms of nomenclatural types is not affected by the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal, since those other codes do not contain the concept of *Candidatus* names and do not contain a concept analogous to pro-validly published names. Under “Best of Both Worlds”, the concept of validly published names would remain as it is in the ICNP; it would continue to correspond to the concept of validly published names in the ICNafp and to the concept of available names in the ICZN.

W&V: *For the same reason, reusing a name for a different type is usually avoided. Although occasional changes in types, i.e. designation of neotypes, have been tolerated in prokaryotic systematics for decades, these are not common. Section 10 is proposing changes in types for thousands of *Candidatus* names, which will lead to intolerable confusion. Not only does it require the change in nomenclatural type when a representative isolate becomes available, but Rule 70 also promotes the replacement of nomenclatural types when a preferred type (discussed below) is obtained. The permanent association of names to their types is the basis for their precise meanings.*

Not an argument. – The association of names with nomenclatural types is indeed one basis of their precise meaning. However, the value of this association also depends on the kind and quality of the nomenclatural type (Table 2). It therefore makes sense to allow for replacing nomenclatural types if

- a) the associated name is regarded preliminary, as in the case of *Candidatus* names;

- b) the replaced type is of higher quality than the previous type;
- c) the replacement type evidently belongs to the same species or subspecies as the previous type.

If all of these conditions hold, replacing the type makes sense, as provided for by Section 10.

In addition to Rules 18c-18e of the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023), which regulate how a neotype strain is assigned, we also have Rule 18f and 18g, also about replacing the nomenclatural type. The similarity of particularly Rules 18c-18f to the proposed Rule 70 should be obvious. Further details on these issues will be provided below.

W&V: *When types change, the circumscription inevitably changes as well, and names become ambiguous (Figure 1).*

Not an argument. – The circumscription of taxa is not regulated by the ICNP. As stated in General Consideration 4:

‘Rules of nomenclature **do not govern the delimitation of taxa** nor determine their relations. The Rules prescribe the procedures for creating and proposing new names and for assessing the correctness of the names applied to defined taxa.’

This implies that the ICNP already regards the “procedures ... for assessing the correctness of the names applied to defined taxa” as being independent of how taxa are delimited. These procedures would still be fully in place if Section 10 was approved, much like any other current regulations of the ICNP. The ICNP does not consider changes of circumscriptions as making names unjustifiable ambiguous.

Even mere emendations of taxa can alter the circumscription of a taxon, whether done informally or formally, as addressed by Rule 35 of the ICNP:

‘If an **alteration of the diagnostic characters or of the circumscription of a taxon modifies the nature of the taxon**, the author(s) responsible may be indicated by the addition to the author citation of the abbreviation “emend.” (emendavit) followed by the name of the author(s) responsible for the change.’

For this reason, the circumscription of a taxon can change at any time, even irrespective of the nomenclatural type. While the association of names with nomenclatural types is one basis of their precise meaning, another basis is the circumscription of a taxon, which is not regulated by the ICNP. This means a taxon name is not intended to have a precise meaning without a reference to a certain taxonomic opinion about the delineation or circumscription of a taxon, which can be freely chosen.

This is a consequence of taxonomic freedom, which is listed, as one of the four essential points of nomenclature, in Principle 1 of the ICNP. Principle 1 balances four aspects against each other. Stability of names is one of these aspects, but it is counterbalanced by the three others. Among them is taxonomic freedom:

‘(4) Nothing in this Code may restrict the freedom of taxonomic thought or action.’

Taxonomic freedom always acts in both ways: some authors may freely reclassify taxa in some

manner, but others are free to classify differently.

The ICSP has an *Ad Hoc Committee on Mitigating Changes in Prokaryotic Nomenclature*. This ad hoc committee, headed by Markus Göker as chairman and Susan Butler-Wu as secretary, works on informing stakeholders about the positive aspects of taxonomic freedom and how it helps them choose the names of prokaryotes they prefer to work with (<https://zenodo.org/records/13241701>). Taxonomic freedom can well be used to provide for the stability of names a particular group of microbiologists works with. For instance, taxonomic freedom gives this group the option to classify and name as they are used to do, instead of applying the last name proposed for a taxon at all cost.

Taxonomic freedom also means that one does not need to delineate taxa in the way implied by Figure 1 of Whitman & Venter.

Apart from that, the example given by Whitman & Venter (2024) in their Figure 1 does not work, as shown below. Real biological distances are never distributed as in the grid-like Figure 1 on which Whitman & Venter's argument is based. In fact, the figure shows completely equidistant and unstructured data. No 'clusters' are recognisable, as the distances between each point (representing an organism) and its respective neighbours are always nearly identical. This figure is misleading, since nobody could conduct taxonomy in such a data set because it does not contain any discernible taxa. The clustering approach applied by Whitman & Venter to their own example leads to taxonomic paradoxes that cannot be resolved (Figure I).

In a real-world data set, the situation is completely different. Whitman & Venter (2024) are not explicit about the assumptions they make. However, it is implied in their misleading example that they assume non-ultrametric (dis-)similarities in conjunction with a certain clustering approach. Even in a real-world data set, this approach to clustering creates its own problems when used in conjunction with non-ultrametric data. When a more appropriate clustering approach is used, the problem attempted to be illustrated in their Figure 1 disappears.

W&V: *Figure 1. Why it is a bad idea to change nomenclatural types. Changes in type are accompanied by changes in circumscription of the species, resulting in changes in the meaning of the name. A. Selection of a nomenclature type implies that similar organisms will be included in the circumscription of the group. B. Change in type from T1 to T2 also changes the circumscription because the species now includes those organisms like T2. Some organisms in the circumscription of T1 are excluded from the circumscription of T2. C. Change in type from T2 to T3 changes the circumscription again, and the type T1 is no longer included in the circumscription of T3 even though the name has not changed.*

The example does not work. – In brief, Figure 1 from the letter by Whitman & Venter (2024) shows a contrived data set that does not contain any discernible taxonomic structure because each dot (i.e., organism) is equidistant or virtually equidistant to its neighbours. No meaningful taxonomy can be concluded with such a data set at all (see our Figure I).

Their Figure 1 is not well explained but from the text we can infer that Whitman & Venter mean this:

- Each dot represents an organism. This is clear from, e.g. “Some organisms in the circumscription of T1 are excluded from the circumscription of T2”; these are the five blue

points within the shaded circle but not within the black circle.

- The blue points stand for organisms that are not nomenclatural types, the orange points stand for nomenclatural types and the light orange points stand for former nomenclatural types. This is evident from the descriptions T1, T2, T3.
- The distances between the points in the plain of the figure are supposed to be proportional to biological distances between the organisms. This is evident from the usage of the circles in conjunction with “similar organisms”. What is within the circle is less distant, hence more similar to the centre of the circle than what is outside the circle.
- The circumscription of a species comprises all organisms within a circle of a certain diameter with the type as centre. This is evident from the usage of the circles in conjunction with the use of the term “circumscription”.

The problem with this artificial data set is that it does not contain any discernible structure and therefore cannot be subjected to any meaningful classification at all (Figure I). This problem is entirely independent of any change of a nomenclatural type. We see this immediately if we look into Whitman & Venter’s Figure 1A and ask the question to which species the organisms belong that are not placed within the circle surrounding T1. For instance, if another nomenclatural type is placed two dots away from T1, then the dot (organism) between them simultaneously belongs to two species at the same time if we apply Whitman & Venter’s own circle-drawing criterion for species delimitation. As shown in our Figure I, an organism can even simultaneously belong to three species.

Figure I. Left, redrawn from Figure 1 in Whitman & Venter (2024). Each blue dot represents an organism, while the distances between the dots are supposed to represent biological distances. Obviously, you cannot conduct taxonomy in such a data set but Whitman & Venter use it as an example anyway. Centre, paradoxes are unavoidable in such a data set. S1 and S2 are the nomenclatural types of two species. If we apply Whitman & Venter’s own circling method to their own data set, one organism ends up simultaneously belonging to two species. Right, paradoxes are unavoidable in such a data set. S1, S3 and S4 are the nomenclatural types of three species. If we apply Whitman & Venter’s own circling method to their own data set, one organism ends up simultaneously belonging to three species, while several organisms end up belonging to two species.

In a real-world data set, there are discernible taxa (as in Figure II). The change of nomenclatural types envisaged by Section 10 includes two kinds of changes:

1. Changes of the kind of nomenclatural type or quality thereof based on the same organism, i.e. switching from deposited DNA sequence of that organism to a more complete DNA sequence or a deposited specimen of the same organism. Obviously, such a change cannot create any ambiguity.
2. Changes of the kind of nomenclatural type or quality thereof based on an organism that would according to the original authors of the name belong to the same species or subspecies. Obviously, such a change cannot create any ambiguity beyond the ambiguity that is inherent in the one simply due to the fact that a code of nomenclature does not regulate the circumscription of taxa.

Such considerations easily demonstrate that Figure 1 of Whitman & Venter (2024) fails to prove anything.

Figure II. Left, a data set in which one can actually conduct taxonomy because there are discernible taxa. Each dot represents an organism, while the distances between the dots represent biological distances. S5, S6 and S7 are the locations of the nomenclatural types of the three clearly recognizable species. Centre, exchanges of nomenclatural types envisaged to be possible by Section 10 need not affect their phylogenetic positioning. For instance, if instead of a genome sequence a strain from which this genome sequence has previously been obtained becomes the nomenclatural type, the phylogenetic position of this genome sequence does not change. Right, even if a change of a nomenclatural type changes the phylogenetic position, this is still restricted to changes that do not change the species affiliation of the nomenclatural type according to the adopted taxonomic view. The three species are still discernible and it is still known to which species which nomenclatural type belongs.

Whitman & Venter (2024) also overlook that the 2nd shift (rightmost part of their Figure 1) would not even be allowed according to the proposed Section 10. Every nomenclatural type must be conspecific with the first nomenclatural type according to the views of the original authors.

W&V: *It has previously been claimed that the ICNP is fully aligned with the other codes of nomenclature, but this will no longer be true if rules to change type material are introduced. Most importantly, changing types is unnecessary and serves no practical purpose.*

Not correct. – Actually, “rules to change type material” (nomenclatural types) are already included in the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023).

Rules 18c-18e regulate how a neotype strain is assigned. In Rule 18c we find:

‘If a strain on which the original description was based cannot be found, a neotype strain may be proposed. ... The author(s) should also demonstrate that the proposed neotype agrees closely with the description given by the original author(s).’

The similarity of this Rule to the proposed Rule 70 should be obvious.

Rule 18f regulates the replacement of a description or illustration of a dead preserved specimen by a strain as nomenclatural type:

‘If a description or illustration constitutes, or a dead preserved specimen has been designated the type of a species (Rule 18a(1)) and later a strain of this species is cultivated, then the type strain may be designated by the person who isolated the strain or by a subsequent author. This type strain shall then replace the description, illustration or preserved specimen as the nomenclatural type.’

(As an aside, note that this would imply the option to replace a genome sequence by strain should the ICSP make the flawed decision to accept names validly published under the SeqCode!)

Again, the similarity of this Rule to the proposed Rule 70 should be obvious. No requirement is made other than that the strain is “of this species”. Like Rule 70, the motivation behind Rule 18f is that the new nomenclatural type is of better quality.

There is also Rule 18g, also about replacing the nomenclatural type.

Even more importantly, changing the nomenclatural type of a *Candidatus* name is already implicit in Appendix 11 of the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023). The required data for *Candidatus* name are not called a nomenclatural type but they can be considered as such:

‘The following information should be included in the description of a *Candidatus* taxon: (a) Genomic information, i.e., nucleic acid sequences apt to determine the phylogenetic position of the organism. ...’

While not required, it is also possible to explicitly assign a nomenclatural type to a *Candidatus* name, and many authors have done that. Upon valid publication, such an *ad hoc* nomenclatural type would then be exchanged by a deposited strain as nomenclatural type. For instance, in the description of “*Candidatus* *Helicobacter heilmannii*” (O’Rourke et al. 2004) we read:

‘NAS of 16S rRNA gene and partial urease gene for the reference strain, isolate HU2^R, obtained from a human patient, GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession nos AF506786 and AF508012, respectively.’

This name was later validly published (Smet et al. 2010), using the original sequence information to determine identity at the species level and for designating a type strain:

‘... *H. heilmannii* has been shown to induce MALT lymphomas when propagated in mice for up to 28 months (O’Rourke et al., 2004a).

The type strain is ASB1^T (=DSM 23983^T=LMG 26292^T), isolated from the gastric mucosa of a cat.’

While Smet et al. (2010) voluntarily reused the *Candidatus* name, such reuse of a name would be mandatory if Section 10 were to be ratified. The advantages of this regulation, including the replacement of the nomenclatural type, should be obvious.

Moreover, in Whitman’s (2016) original proposal to allow for DNA sequences as nomenclatural types of taxa with a validly published name, replacement of such nomenclatural types was envisaged:

‘Rule 18f. If a sequence of genomic DNA, description or illustration constitutes, or a dead preserved specimen has been designated, the type of a species [Rules 18a(1) and 18a(3)] and a later strain of this species is cultivated, then the type strain may be designated by the person who isolated the strain or by a subsequent author. **This type strain shall then replace the sequence of genomic DNA, description, illustration or preserved specimen as the nomenclatural type.**’

One might therefore wonder why the exchange of a nomenclatural type should be acceptable or unacceptable, depending on who proposes it.

Moreover, when considering different codes it is important not to compare apples and oranges. The ICNP would remain fully aligned with the ICZN (Ride et al. 2000) and the ICNafp (Turland et al. 2018) in terms of nomenclatural types, since those codes do not contain the concept of *Candidatus* names and do not contain a concept analogous to pro-validly published names. The concept of validly published names would remain as it is in the ICNP; it would continue to correspond to the concept of validly published names in the ICNafp and to the concept of available names in the ICZN.

W&V: *Section 10 stabilizes the nomenclature of Candidatus names for genera and species but adds more complexity for the names of the higher taxonomic ranks. Genera are the types of all the higher taxonomic ranks. Because ‘pro-validly published’ Candidatus genus names cannot be types for validly published names, they cannot be types for validly published names of the higher taxonomic ranks under the ICNP. However, to retain the Candidatus names of higher taxonomic ranks, Section 10 allows changing the type of the Candidatus name to that of a different genus-level taxon whose name can be validly published, i.e. the type can be deposited in culture collections. In this case, Section 10 requires that the original Candidatus taxon must be renamed. As a consequence, the types of the higher taxonomic rank and one genus change, and one type is given a new Candidatus name. Under Section 10, the valid publication of names of all the taxa with Candidatus names is likely to occur over many years as taxa are brought into culture. Thus, the names of higher taxa can be expected to remain in flux for the foreseeable future. Moreover, frequent database curation will be required to keep the names current.*

Not an argument. – “Best of Both Worlds” reduces the number of synonyms and homonyms; where it does allow synonyms to be created it does so for good reasons.

First and foremost, the creation of homonyms and synonyms between validly published names cannot be triggered by the proposed Section 10. Section 10 does not affect the creation of homonyms and synonyms between validly published names.

Second, proposed Rules 72(1), 72(2) and 72(3) directly mandate the reuse of pro-validly published *Candidatus* names, thereby avoiding synonyms.

Third, the preamble to Rule 72 generally prohibits the creation of homonyms between pro-validly published and validly published names.

Fourth, the SeqCode itself leads to synonyms and homonyms because it contravenes the ICNP (Arahal et al. 2024). Whitman & Venter (2024) do not mention this issue.

The creation of homonyms and synonyms would theoretically be possible under “Best of Both Worlds”, but only when taxa of several ranks are involved, and even then only under special conditions. These have been defined in Rule 72(4). They are not affected by other rules. The revised version of the Best of Both Worlds proposal has rewritten Rule 74(4) because we believe the additional “top-down” option to be unnecessary. Those who do the hard work of cultivation and deposit may not be interested in this “top-down” option anyway; see the example of *Promethearchaeum* for details (<https://microbiologysociety.org/blog/appreciation-towards-culture-collections.html>).

Rule 72(4) was originally proposed as follows.

‘The reuse of a pro-validly published and pro-legitimate *Candidatus* name at a given rank when proposing a name for valid publication, without considering the two names to be synonymous, is permitted where this is a necessary condition for proposing the reuse of a pro-validly published and pro-legitimate *Candidatus* name considered to be synonymous at another rank, provided that both names are proposed in the same effective publication.’

The original note to this rule should not have been overlooked:

‘*Note.* Although Rule 72(4) provides for a possible exception to Rule 72(1), Rule 72(2) or Rule 72(3), it is recommended to **choose**, among the solutions in accordance with the Rules, **the solution which retains the most commonly used names or**, if this cannot be determined, the solution **that results in the overall lowest number of replacement names.**’

In other words, it is generally recommended not to take the route provided for in Rule 72(4). The use of Rule 72(4) may often not retain the most commonly used names, and will never result in the “overall lowest number of replacement names”, which is zero.

There are few situations in which it may have made sense to follow Rule 72(4):

- there are no commonly used names that would need to be replaced;
- there are not many names that would need to be replaced;
- anchoring a name of a higher taxon in a type genus with a validly published name is of particular importance in this situation;
- there is an inherent problem with the current type genus.

This means that there is a well-defined trade-off between retaining more names, or more important names, and validly publishing a name at a higher rank. The stability of *Candidatus* names that are rarely used is not a primary concern. Also, the lowest possibly total number of replacement names is zero, and there would need to be good reasons to override this. Overriding recommendations always requires a reason to do so.

However, as indicated above, Rule 72(4) along with its example has been revised. Removing the “top-down” option does not change the value of the remaining proposal. “Best of Both Worlds” intends to retain a strong incentive to cultivate and deposit. The revised version best serves this interest. It does not lead to any homonyms and leads to synonyms only if this is unavoidable; furthermore, it supports those who cultivate and deposit particularly difficult organisms.

W&V: *Section 10 also contains biases that are difficult to understand and will confound its implementation. For example, Rule 69 establishes preferences for four different kinds of Candidatus type material. Types with lower preferences can be replaced with types of higher preferences. Under Rule 69(1)a, non-pure cultures are the preferred type and can only have Candidatus names. This rule seems to include obligate symbionts. Currently, names of obligate symbionts can be validly published, and Microcaldus is a recent example (Sakai et al., 2022). Presumably, this name would become illegitimate or ‘pro-legitimate’ if this amendment is accepted. This rule also seems to be oblivious to recent discoveries of abundant obligate symbionts, which are revising our views of prokaryotic biology (Brown et al., 2015, Gios et al., 2023, Hug et al., 2016, Rinke et al., 2013).*

Not correct. – The rule that determines valid publication, Rule 30, is unchanged by Section 10. Rule 69(1) does *not* state that “non-pure cultures ... can only have *Candidatus* names”.

Instead, Rule 69(1) states that a non-pure culture *can* be the nomenclatural type of a pro-validly published *Candidatus* name. This does not mean that non-pure cultures, such as co-cultures, cannot be the nomenclatural type of a validly published name. The preference given for impure cultures in Rule 69(1) is only a preference over the other possible nomenclatural types for pro-validly published *Candidatus* names.

As clearly indicated in the proposed Rule 66, the *Candidatus* status should *not* be used if the requirements of Rule 27(3) are met:

‘The *Candidatus* status should be used to propose names of prokaryotic taxa for which some information is available (Rules 67–68), but for which the requirements for valid publication of a name under Rule 27(3) are not met.’

Accordingly, Section 10 does not apply to anything regulated by Rule 27(3). It does not override Rule 27(3). In particular, Section 10 does not retroactively change the criteria for valid publication.

Moreover, one must not confound the question of legitimacy with the question of valid publication. The requirements for nomenclatural types are linked to valid publication via Rule 27(3), which would remain entirely unchanged if Section 10 were to be adopted. For species and subspecies, Rule 27(3) refers to Rule 30, which would also remain entirely unchanged. Hence, the criteria for the nomenclatural type – such as whether it is a pure or impure culture or something else – affect valid publication, not legitimacy. As indicated in ICNP Rule 23a Note 5 (Oren et al. 2023), only validly published names can be illegitimate or legitimate. As indicated in proposed Section 10, only

pro-validly published names could be pro-illegitimate or pro-legitimate.

We have carefully assessed the wording of the proposed Section 10. Rule 69(1)(a) is now phrased as follows:

‘A culture containing living cells of the species or subspecies from which characters of use in taxonomy can be obtained, but which does not meet the requirements of Rule 30.’

This makes the delegation to Rule 30 (to which Rule 27(3) also delegates) more obvious, although this has already been obvious from the proposed Note to Rule 70 and the proposed Rule 66.

W&V: *Under Rule 69(1)b, the next level of preferred types is preserved specimens, but this rule requires that museums or other collections be established to house them. These collections will need resources that do not currently exist.*

Not an argument. – It may well be that these resources do not exist, but in this case the authors of a *Candidatus* name are simply supposed to go further down the list in Rule 69(1) and use a genome sequence as nomenclatural type.

No part of Rule 69 indicates that the nomenclatural type of a *Candidatus* name *must* be a preserved specimen. Moreover, the authors may simply prefer not to make use of such resources, even if they existed. Even if corresponding “museums or other collections” were established, authors could use a sequence as nomenclatural type.

This is clearly stated not only in Rule 69(1) but also in the main text in the article by Arahal et al. (2024) before the proposed Section 10:

‘In order to allow for backward compatibility, an implementation is of interest that **yields a strong preference for genome sequences in taxonomic practice** but also allows the use of non-pure cultures (such as enrichment cultures), preserved specimens, gene sequences, textual descriptions or illustrations.’

And the only error in this sentence is that it still lists “textual descriptions or illustrations”. This is an erroneous leftover from a previous version of the manuscript by Arahal et al. (2024) and is not included in the proposed Section 10 in that publication. The proposed and revised Section 10 will be voted on by the ICSP, not this sentence cited above. The proposed and revised Section 10 does not include textual descriptions or illustrations as nomenclatural types.

Moreover, if “museums or other collections” do not normally house preserved specimens, then the concerns expressed by Whitman & Venter (2024) about changing from a genome sequence or gene sequence to a preserved specimen as nomenclatural type are unfounded, since deposit of this preserved specimen is required by Rule 69(2). As shown elsewhere, these concerns are unfounded in general, but this additional contradiction in the article by Whitman & Venter is worth mentioning.

W&V: *Rules 69(1)c and d allow genome and DNA sequences to serve as types, but they are the least preferred. The rationale for preferring types of mixed cultures or preserved specimens over genome sequences, which can precisely identify taxa and are widely used in most current taxonomic studies, is not clear. The advantages of DNA sequences over these alternative types are well-documented in the literature, particularly for uncultivated taxa.*

Not correct. – One can obtain DNA sequences, including genome sequences, from mixed cultures or preserved specimens, but not vice versa. For this reason, mixed cultures or preserved specimens have all the advantages of DNA sequences but have additional advantages of their own (Table 2).

Once DNA sequences have been obtained, they may well “precisely identify taxa and are widely used in most current taxonomic studies”. The crucial difference is that when pure cultures, mixed cultures or preserved specimens have been made available to others as nomenclatural types, one can conduct DNA sequencing again, determine whether the original results are reproducible, conduct other studies than DNA sequencing with them, and have the chance to improve the data by correcting or adding to them.

W&V: *Nevertheless, if the original type for a Candidatus name is a sequence of a gene, Section 10 will allow replacement of the type three times, first with a genome sequence, then a preserved specimen, and then a mixed culture. Finally, if a pure culture can be deposited, the type can be changed a fourth time upon valid publication. Importantly, these changes in type fail to provide any practical benefits for the scientific community.*

Not correct. – The rationale for the preferences for nomenclatural types given in Rule 69(1) is not difficult to understand.

Rule 69(1) in the proposed Section 10, in conjunction with the unchanged Rule 27(3) of the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023), gives the following preferences for nomenclatural types of species or subspecies:

1. pure living cultures or impure cultures conforming to Rule 27(3), such as co-cultures, are better than impure living cultures not conforming to Rule 27(3);
2. impure living cultures not conforming to Rule 27(3) are better than preserved specimens;
3. preserved specimens are better than genome sequences;
4. genome sequences are better than single gene sequences.

The reason for this order is simple:

- a) Pure living cultures are obviously preferable to the other options. One can always generate an impure living culture (e.g., a co-culture), a preserved specimen, a genome sequence or a single gene sequence from a pure culture, but not vice versa (the sole exception being that one can sometimes generate a pure living culture from an impure living culture).
- b) Regarding Rule 69(1), a preserved specimen can be generated from an impure culture, but not vice versa.
- c) A genome sequence can be generated from a culture or a preserved specimen, but not vice versa.
- d) A single gene sequence can be generated from a culture or preserved specimen or genome sequence, but not vice versa.

The system is entirely logical and reflects the ICSP's (and thus the ICNP's) previous preferences for nomenclatural types (Oren et al. 2023; Sutcliffe et al. 2020).

One must not overlook the actual wording of proposed Rule 70(2):

‘The proposal of a replacement type in the IJSEM must state the reason for the replacement in sufficient detail. The proposal must also provide evidence that the replacement type belongs to the species or subspecies according to the taxonomic view expressed in the effective publication of the name of the species or subspecies.’

For this reason, Rule 70(2) allows authors to

1. replace a gene sequence by a genome sequence or preserved specimen or impure culture of what is evidently the same species or subspecies according to the view of the original authors;
2. replace a genome sequence by a preserved specimen or impure culture of what is evidently the same species or subspecies according to the view of the original authors;
3. replace a preserved specimen by an impure culture of what is evidently the same species or subspecies according to the view of the original authors.

All of these steps improve the data that are made available to others (Table 2). This has obvious “practical benefits for the scientific community.”

As for the fact that the impure cultures mentioned in Rule 70(2) are only those not considered conforming to Rule 27(3), see above.

In addition, the criteria for valid publication under the ICNP, unchanged by Section 10, provide for the replacement of an impure culture not regarded as in accordance with Rule 27(3) by a culture regarded as in accordance with Rule 27(3), whether pure or a co-culture, as in the case of *Nanobdella* (Kato et al. 2022), in order to validly publish a name previously present as *Candidatus* name.

Table 2. Kinds of nomenclatural types and their advantages or disadvantages.

Kind of nomenclatural type	Kind of object	Contains the organism	Allows reproducing biological experiments
Pure living cultures	Physical material	Yes	Yes
Impure living cultures	Physical material	Yes	Yes
Preserved specimens	Physical material	Yes	Yes
Genome sequence	Electronically stored experimental outcome	No	No
Single gene sequence	Electronically stored experimental outcome	No	No

As shown in Table 2, physical material (pure cultures, impure cultures, preserved specimens) allows for the reproduction of experimental results (such as genome sequences or single gene sequences). If only genome sequences or single gene sequences are available, it is not possible to reproduce the experiments. Only experimental results would be available, not the organism or parts thereof. These

experimental results would be artificially fixed once they have passed a (partially arbitrary) quality criterion at a certain time point. The best option is always the possibility to re-run entire experiments, starting with the biological material, and not just with the sequence reads.

This is one of the major disadvantages of the SeqCode. Further information is given in the section “Cultures are preferred to DNA sequences” in the paper by Arahal et al. (2024).

W&V: *Lastly, Section 10 fails to provide criteria for quality of the types. When the SeqCode was developed, a consensus prevailed that genome sequences had to meet high experimental standards to serve as types (Hedlund et al., 2022). For instance, under normal circumstances a highly contaminated or incomplete MAG or the sequence of a 16S rRNA gene cannot serve as a type under the SeqCode. Section 10 would allow inferior data to serve as the experimental basis of Candidatus names. Only poor taxonomic decisions can follow from poor data.*

Not correct. – The ICNP (Oren et al. 2023) already has higher quality requirements for the valid publication of a name (as, e.g., obvious from Rule 30) than the SeqCode, and our proposals in the Best of Both Worlds would not change that (Arahal et al. 2024).

The key issue here is not to compare apples and oranges. One can easily compare a set of requirements for validly published names with another set of requirements for validly published names, but a comparison of a set of requirements for valid publication with a set of requirements for pro-valid publication must be treated with caution.

By retaining the treatment of names based solely on a genome sequence as *Candidatus* names, it remains clear that these are provisional names that require further refinement. This is reflected in our proposal for Rule 70. This rule is in turn based on the logical order of kinds of nomenclatural types as given in Rule 69(1) and discussed above (Table 2).

The manuscript by Arahal et al. (2024) clearly explains why further requirements cannot or should not be made in a code of nomenclature itself:

‘As explained above, the specificity of a DNA sequence depends on assumptions about the delimitation of taxa, which a code of nomenclature is not permitted to make. Under the reasonable assumption that sequence completeness is positively correlated with specificity, a code of nomenclature should not define requirements for completeness other than those implied by the requirement for inclusion in public sequence repositories [69]. Further details about the use of genome or other DNA sequences as nomenclatural types of *Candidatus* names should be delegated to minimal standards published by taxonomic committees or included in journals’ instructions for authors; similar minimal standards were published in the past [75]. The ICSP-associated subcommittee [4] that would oversee such standards could then respond more flexibly to technological developments than the ICNP itself, as emendations of the ICNP require proper legislation [4].’

This means that sequence quality is not ignored. Rather, it is delegated to an institution outside the ICNP. This is exactly how the IJSEM already handles the issue of minimum standards for genome sequences: the minimum standards for genome sequences for taxonomic purposes are outside the ICNP (<https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.002516>; <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.006300>). This makes them easier to update, not harder. Placing them outside the ICNP therefore does not mean that the

Section 10 proposal does not care about quality. Rather, it means that Section 10 cares a lot about quality. And Section 10 also recognizes that a code of nomenclature does not regulate how taxa are delimited (see, ICNP, General Consideration 4).

Since this may, apparently, otherwise be overlooked, we have added the following sentence to the Note to Rule 69:

‘The nomenclatural type should conform to minimal standards, when these are available for the respective kind of nomenclatural type at the time of effective publication.’

This is modelled on how the ICNP handles the questions of minimum standards in Rule 27 Note 1:

‘The description of the taxon should conform to minimal standards (see Recommendation 30).’

It may also be overlooked that Best of Both Worlds requires INSDC accession numbers and calls for the exchange of nomenclatural types once they become unsuitable. We therefore have added to Rule 70(1)(a) a sentence that reiterates that unavailability of the nomenclatural type may include suppression of a sequence record by INSDC, resulting in:

‘The possible reasons for replacing the nomenclatural type of a *Candidatus* species or subspecies are the following: (1) The nomenclatural type is no longer available. This includes deposits of living cultures or specimens that are no longer available, and sequence records that have been suppressed by INSDC. ...’

We suspect that most readers would have expected this anyway, but the wording adds clarity and addresses the alleged problems with sequence quality. It will be obvious to most readers that a major reason for INSDC to suppress sequences is quality.

For further evidence, please see proposed Rule 70 as well as subsection “Sequence-only approaches reduce reproducibility”, subsection “Sequence purity is addressed together with sequence completeness”, and subsection “Replacement of nomenclatural types should occur under defined conditions” in Arahall et al. (2024).

W&V: *In summary, Section 10 introduces a complex system intended to incorporate Candidatus names into the formal nomenclature of prokaryotes. This goal is accomplished by discarding the permanent association of types to names, introducing ambiguity and instability. It sacrifices the clarity of ICNP and, if adopted, represents a step backwards in prokaryotic systematics.*

Not correct. – As reiterated above, the “permanent association of types to names” is not actually permanent under the ICNP even for validly published names. The exchange of the nomenclatural type of a *Candidatus* name upon valid publication is already envisaged by the ICNP. The “Best of Both Worlds” approach does not change this.

In contrast to the proposed SeqCode, the Best of Both Worlds proposal is fully compatible with the 2022 revision of the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023) and previous ICSP decisions (Sutcliffe et al. 2020). Because of its obvious disadvantages, none of which are addressed by Whitman & Venter (2024), the SeqCode “represents a step backwards in prokaryotic systematics”.

W&V: *It will also create a second nomenclatural code with overlap of names already regulated under the SeqCode, promulgating further confusion.*

Not correct. – In contrast, many names “validly published” under the SeqCode could easily be made pro-validly published under the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023) if Section 10 were to be ratified.

Since, as explained above, the acceptance of the proposed SeqCode by the ICNP would have severely negative consequences for the future of microbiology, an alternative is needed. If names “validly published” under the SeqCode became pro-validly published under the ICNP, this would not increase confusion, but decrease it, since then the SeqCode name would need to be reused upon valid publication under the ICNP. Moreover, homonyms would be avoided.

Accordingly, even in case of the continued existence of the SeqCode, the acceptance of our proposal would be an improvement on the current situation in which the two codes are prone to generate homonyms and synonyms (Arahal et al. 2024).

It is indeed the proposed SeqCode itself which has created a conflict in prokaryotic nomenclature. The SeqCode contravenes the ICNP by construction (Göker et al. 2022) and will lead to synonyms and homonyms with regard to the ICNP (Arahal et al. 2024). It will also lead to different names being considered the correct name. The “Best of Both Worlds” does not create such conflict. It is fully compatible with previous ICSP decisions.

For this reason, it is Section 10 which addresses the need “to construct taxonomies uniting cultivated and uncultivated prokaryotes”.

W&V: *In contrast, the SeqCode accomplishes all the goals of Section 10 more simply without sacrificing the precision and unambiguity of the ICNP. It provides stable names for taxa that cannot be named under the ICNP and means of designating the nature of the type. It ensures the quality of the DNA sequences that can serve as types. It provides the SeqCode Registry, a convenient online resource to track names that is compatible with databases and replaces the rather archaic system of published validation lists. This important service can review nomenclature proposals before they are published and provide comprehensive automatic as well as manual checks of both sequences and nomenclature. The SeqCode also requires deposition and free availability of raw sequence data in INSDC databases, which allows reanalysis of the raw data. Because it is a database, the SeqCode Registry can communicate with other databases, which facilitates the wide dissemination of names and type genomes. Because genome sequences are known for most type strains, the integration of SeqCode and ICNP names in stable taxonomies is straightforward.*

Not correct. – The SeqCode contravenes the ICNP by construction (Göker et al. 2022). The SeqCode has numerous disadvantages, comprehensively listed by Arahal et al. (2024). Whitman & Venter (2024) chose not to address any of these disadvantages.

Two competing codes with overlapping scopes are not conducive for microbiology as a whole and a source of confusion and error. The derogatory comments about the Validation Lists published in the IJSEM are also misplaced. The ICSP works closely together with LPSN (Meier-Kolthoff et al. 2022) to achieve easy interoperability with other databases, among many other features. The proposed SeqCode (Hedlund et al. 2022) is an unoriginal work that has copied excessively from the ICNP.

W&V: *The SeqCode currently recognizes names formed under the ICNP. The ICSP should amend the ICNP to recognize names formed under the SeqCode just as it recognizes names of*

Cyanobacteria formed under the ICN, which represents a precedent for recognition of names from other codes.

Not correct. – The International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants (ICNafp; Turland et al. 2018) demands physical material (preserved specimens) as nomenclatural types for newly proposed names and has already rejected multiple proposals to consider DNA sequences as nomenclatural types. The results of the votes on the last set of proposals (Turland et al. 2024) are included in Table 3. Therefore, the recognition of cyanobacterial names validly published under the ICNafp by the ICNP (Oren et al. 2023) cannot serve as a precedent to recognize the proposed SeqCode.

Table 3. Results of the preliminary guiding vote (“mail vote”) on selected proposals to amend the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants submitted to the XX International Botanical Congress, Madrid 2024. Proposals 329–338 (Thiele & al. in Taxon 72: 1143-1145) to permit DNA sequences to serve as types of names in prescribed circumstances [“Thiele et al. Option 1”] and 339–348 (Thiele & al. in Taxon 72: 1146-1148) to permit DNA sequences to be used for fixing the application of names in prescribed circumstances [“Thiele et al. Option 2”] received more than 75% “no” votes and were therefore auto-rejected, i.e. not further considered on the congress.

Proposal	Affected ICNafp section	Result of “mail vote”
329	Art. 8, D	81% NO (auto-rej)
330	Art. 9, D	85% NO (auto-rej)
331	Art. 9, HH	84% NO (auto-rej)
332	Art. 9, CCC	83% NO (auto-rej)
333	Art. 29, A	84% NO (auto-rej)
334	Art. 38, C	80% NO (auto-rej)
335	Art. 40, L	83% NO (auto-rej)
336	Ch. 5, section 2, A	82% NO (auto-rej)
337	Art. 44, B	84% NO (auto-rej)
338	Div. III, X	83% NO (auto-rej)
339	Principles, A	76% NO (auto-rej)
340	Chap. II, A	76% NO (auto-rej)
341	Art. 6, c	76% NO (auto-rej)
342	Art. 7, A	80% NO (auto-rej)
343	Chap. II, new Art., A	77% NO (auto-rej)
344	Art. 38, D	82% NO (auto-rej)

345	Art. 39, A	80% NO (auto-rej)
346	Art. 40, C	86% NO (auto-rej)
347	Art. 44, c	84% NO (auto-rej)
348	Div. III, Y	82% NO (auto-rej)

The petition “Support the Best of Both Worlds” (<https://www.ipetitions.com/petition/support-the-best-of-both-worlds>) was also signed by researchers who work on the ICNafp. Some have used this opportunity to critically comment on the SeqCode. Jan Mareš (Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences) wrote:

‘I am adding my name as a representative of the Nomenclature Committee for Algae, helping to maintain the International Code of Nomenclature for Algae, Fungi, and Plants. This matter concerns also Cyanobacteria, which are currently covered by both ICn and ICNP. Recently, both Codes were harmonized, but SeqCode represents a danger of large confusion in the nomenclature of Cyanobacteria and other bacterial groups.’

So, ICNafp experts also recognize the significant difference between the SeqCode on the one hand and the ICNP and the ICNafp on the other hand.

W&V: *Therefore, we request that the International Committee of Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP) reject the proposal of Arahal et al. (2024). The microbiologists listed below have endorsed the opinions expressed in this commentary.*

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“Best of Both Worlds” is more attractive than the SeqCode. – Given the alleged importance of the SeqCode, the number of people who have endorsed the article by Whitman & Venter (2024) is quite small. The petition titled “Support the Best of Both Worlds” (<https://www.ipetitions.com/petition/support-the-best-of-both-worlds>) has attracted much more attention. Support came from throughout the world, including microbiologists from Brazil, India and South Africa, who are affected by national regulations that make it difficult for them to validly publish names under the ICNP. As shown above, the people who have contributed to or endorsed the article by Whitman & Venter may wish to re-consider, as their potential good intentions will be served much more sustainably by the “Best of Both Worlds” proposal.

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